

A CASE OF LEIOMYOSARCOMA CAUSING ILEO-CAECAL INTUSSUSCEPTION: THE WRONG TUMOR AT THE WRONG SITE

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ABSTRACT Intussusception remains a very rare presentation in adults where the cause is usually a pathological lead point. A common consensus that appears in the literature dictates that most cases of large bowel and ileo-caecal intussusception are secondary to a malignant lesion compared to small bowel intussusception. Pre-operatively determining the nature of the lead point is not always possible but intussusception itself can be readily diagnosed with the use of CT scanning. Surgical resection with or without initial attempts at reduction of the intussusception remains the treatment of choice. A leiomyosarcoma reported only a handful of times in the past, is a rare cause of the same. We present a case of a patient with known metastatic leiomyosarcoma who was incidentally found to have ileo-caecal intussusception during a surveillance CT scan which was subsequently treated with surgical resection and was found to have a metastatic LMS as the lead point.

KEYWORDS Intussusception, leiomyosarcoma, CT scanning , surgical treatment

Introduction

Intussusception remains a rare pathology in the adult patient. Mostly secondary to a pathological lead point, ileocolic intussusception occurring due to metastatic LMS to the bowel is almost unheard of in the literature, only being reported a handful of times. The rarity of the disease makes this an interesting case and the surgical management employed remains the mainstay of treatment of such cases. This case reports not only brings to light a rare form of surgical pathology but also highlights the challenges that can be faced when dealing with similar lesions, especially when a pre-operative diagnosis is not at hand.

Case presentation

An 82-year-old gentleman who was a known case of metastatic leiomyosarcoma(LMS) from an intravascular primary of left lower limb which was excised 16 years ago He developed lung metastases which were excised four years ago with a left upper lobectomy and apical segmentectomy of the left lower lobe for high-grade metastatic leiomyosarcoma. He completed four cycles of adjuvant doxorubicin post-operatively and remain clinically stable for three years. Follow up CT scan demonstrated stable lung nodules but identified a polypoid lesion in the transverse colon. An 8cm histologically proven metastatic lesion in the transverse colon was removed endoscopically, followed by a Transanal Endoscopic Microsurgery (TEMs) procedure for a 30mm mid rectal lesion identified at the initial colonoscopy, which was a tubular adenoma with high-grade dysplasia. As a follow-up for the TEMs procedure, a further colonoscopy was arranged to check the TEMs excision site and remaining colon. The colonoscopy revealed a 2cm lesion in the caecum, and a similar lesion in the terminal ileum confirmed on biopsy to be metastatic leiomyosarcoma (Fig 1 and Fig 2). An urgent CT scan was arranged to look for recurrence of LMS. The CT performed nine days later, showed large ileocolic intussusception involving not only the terminal ileum but also the mesentery with radi-

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DOI:10.5455/IJMRCR.Leiomyosarcoma-Intussusception

First Received: February 08, 2019

Accepted: March 02, 2019

Manuscript Associate Editor: Ivon Ribarova (BG)

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Fig.1. Caecal polyp on colonoscopy.

ological evidence of impending bowel obstruction. (Fig 3 and Fig 4) The patient was brought in for urgent surgical review and intervention.

The patient reported intermittent abdominal discomfort, bloating, borborygmi and reduced bowel opening change in bowel habits. He underwent right hemicolectomy with primary anastomosis. Intraoperatively, the terminal ileum was seen invaginating into the caecum as far distal as the mid ascending colon. (Fig 5 and Fig 6) Multiple lesions were palpated in the rest of the small bowel indicating further metastasis. The ileocolic segment was resected en bloc and sent for histology. (Fig 7) Microscopic analysis confirmed the presence of a lesion in the caecum and terminal ileum, previously known, as causative lead points for the intussusception and was histologically proven to be LMS. Immunohistochemistry showed strong expression of H-caldesmon and patchy desmin expression with the negative expression for cytokeratins.

Post-operative recovery was uneventful, and the patient was discharged from the hospital on the 5th postoperative day.

Discussion

Intussusception is an infrequent presentation in the adult patients and accounts for only 1% of all cases of adult bowel obstruction and 5% of all cases of intussusception.[1,2] In contrast to paediatric intussusception, where almost all cases are idiopathic, the adult cases are secondary to a pathological lead point in 70-90% of the patients.[3] As extensively reported in the literature, a consensus that appears is that the majority of the lesions causing SBI are benign such as lipomas, inflammatory polyps, leiomyomas, Meckel's diverticulum and post-operative adhesions. However, 30% of SBI will have a malignant cause to it.[1,2] Lesions causing large bowel and Ileo-caecal (IC) intussusception will have a malignant lead point in 58-68% of cases.[1,2,4] Of the malignant lead points, those which are commonly causative are primary adenocarcinoma, carcinoid, polyps, gastrointestinal stromal tumours (GISTs) and metastatic lesions commonly

Fig.2. Polyp in Terminal Ileum (lead point) seen on colonoscopy.

Fig.3. Transverse section CT.

Fig.4. Coronal Section CT.

Fig.6. Ileocaecal Intussusception as seen intraoperatively.

Fig.5. Intra-operative finding.

Fig.7. Resected segment.

melanoma and very rarely sarcomas.[1,5] Multiple case series reported in the literature classify intussusception into entero-enteric, colo-colic, ileocolic and ileo-caecal types.[2,4] When it does occur in the adult patient, the most common variety seen is the entero-enteric or one which involves the small bowel.[3,6] The clinical presentation is varied, non-specific and will not comprise of the classical triad of abdominal pain, palpable mass and blood in stool as seen in children.[2-4] Intussusception secondary to a lead point can be persistent or transient and, like in our case, will cause vague and mostly chronic symptoms ranging from non-specific abdominal pain, change in bowel habits, nausea & vomiting, distention and bloating to partial or complete bowel obstruction.[1-4,7]

The other aspect of this case report revolves around the presence of LMS as the lead point causing IC intussusception. This is an extremely rare tumour which commonly arises in the retroperitoneal space, female genital tract, vascular walls and soft tissues of the lower extremities and can involve the bowel secondarily.[5,8] Only 0.1-3% of all LMS will arise in the gastrointestinal tract as a primary lesion.[8] For this tumour to metastasise to the bowel from a distant primary site is an even rarer occurrence and is only reported a handful of times in the literature.[8-12] To our knowledge, only one study reports metastasis to the bowel from a lower limb subcutaneous LMS like in our case.[5] The prognosis associated with this type of tumour is poor compared GISTs and hence the importance of attaining a diagnosis in similar presentations.[8]

Different imaging modalities can be employed for diagnosing intussusception. Ultrasonography, although being operator dependent can show the classical doughnut sign. CT scanning is reported to be the most reliable for acquiring a diagnosis with accuracies reaching up to 100% with the ability to outline important disease details such as the site of the lesion, which part of the bowel segments are involved, the presence and origin of the lead point or mass, involvement of adjacent structures and vasculature and viability of the involved tissues including the bowel itself.[6] Like in our case the, CT accurately picked up the condition. Bearing this in mind, reaching a pre-operative diagnosis can be difficult as most cases can be intermittent and like in our case, the finding will be incidental.[8] In most instances, the luxury of a preoperative histological diagnosis will not be available, and therefore extreme caution should be taken when surgically managing intussusception of IC variety in an adult patient, especially if a history of pre-existing malignant disease exists. Having said that, endoscopy is still a viable investigation modality and can identify intussusception and biopsy of the lesion involved which can aid in planning for definitive surgery or can be therapeutic for smaller lesions in itself.[1]

As in our case, the recommended mode of surgical treatment for adult intussusception occurring as a result of a definitive or suspected malignant lesion, irrespective of the type, should involve en bloc resection of the involved segment without initial attempts at reduction.[1,2] Alternatively, another consensus seen in the literature is with SBI, initial attempts at reduction can be made due to the high chance of the causative lesion being benign in nature whereas IC and large bowel intussusception are treated directly with resection. Although in the absence of universal guidelines, it remains controversial whether to reduce before resect.[1-4] The extent of the resection will depend on the clinical picture and intraoperative findings.[1] The literature review provides evidence to the use of a laparoscopic approach being employed for the management of such conditions. How-

ever, no comparison studies exist to compare outcomes of laparoscopic versus laparotomy for surgical management of adult intussusception.[8] The type will determine adjuvant treatment beyond the surgical resection, and features of the tumour found on analysis of the resected specimen and are likely to involve chemotherapy.[8,11]

This case report brings to light a very rare form of tumour, causing a rare form of mechanical near total bowel obstruction and outlines the surgical management employed for its treatment. Investigation and management were in line with what was found in the literature. The rarity of the tissue diagnosis of the lead point makes it an interesting find and is something to suspect for when dealing with intussusception in the terminal ileal and caecal area.

Learning Points

- Leiomyosarcoma is a sporadic tumour and is even more unique as a cause of intestinal intussusception.
- Surgical resection is the mainstay of treatment with or without further chemotherapy based on the clinical setting.
- Histological diagnosis of the lead point will confirm the cause but based on the location of the intussusception; appropriate surgical management can be employed to better outcomes.

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